

CSF Applications to Mediterranean Forests - Worksheet 1.1

Identifying Stakeholders

Try to identify your network of stakeholders. Write down how each one can contribute to the process.

Government & Regulatory Bodies

- 1. _____
- 2. _____
- 3. _____
- 4. _____
- 5. _____

(Examples: Ministry of Environment, Forestry Department, Local Municipalities, Policy/Legislative Committees, National Environment Agencies, etc.)

Local Communities & Landowners

- 1. _____
- 2. _____
- 3. _____
- 4. _____
- 5. _____

(Examples: Individual landowners, farmers, community cooperatives, rural associations, indigenous groups, etc.)

NGOs, Civil Society & Environmental Organizations

- 1. _____
- 2. _____
- 3. _____
- 4. _____
- 5. _____

(Examples: Conservation NGOs, advocacy groups, community-based organizations, civic committees, etc.)

Private Sector & Industry

- 1. _____
- 2. _____
- 3. _____
- 4. _____
- 5. _____

(Examples: Timber companies, bioenergy producers, tourism operators, forest product businesses, investment/financial institutions, etc.)

Research & Academic Institutions

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

(Examples: Universities, research centers, climate institutes, technical schools, professional training programs, etc.)

Other organisations

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

(Examples: International organizations like FAO or UN bodies, intergovernmental alliances, cross-border associations, philanthropic donors, etc.)

Other possible stakeholders

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

(Examples: Media outlets, local schools, youth groups, faith-based organizations, consulting firms, etc.)

Worksheet 1.2

Prioritising stakeholders

Assess the importance of each stakeholder. Remove from your list any of the stakeholders that might not be relevant to your needs. Define the level of interest and influence on a scale from one to three, whereas **1** is **Low** and **3** is **High**. Insert the stakeholders in the map of axes of interest and influence by using the template provided below.

LEVEL OF INTEREST	3. High			
	2. Medium			
1. Low				
		1. Low	2. Medium	3. High
LEVEL OF INFLUENCE				

Worksheet 1.3

Communication strategy for stakeholders

WHAT	
WHO	
HOW	
WHEN	
RESULTS	